

RADIOBLOCKS

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List of acronyms

AARTFAAC	Amsterdam-ASTRON Radio Transients Facility And Analysis Center
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALMA	Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
e-VLBI	European VLBI network
EDGAR	Effelsberg Data Gathering and Analysis Resource
EVN	European VLBI Network
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HBM	High Bandwidth Memory
HPC	High Performance Computing
IP	Internet Protocol
ISBI	Irbene Single Baseline Interferometer
JIVE, JIV-ERIC	Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC
KASI	Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute
KVN	Korean VLBI Network
LOFAR	Low Frequency Array
MPI	Message Passing Interface
NIC	Network Interface Connectors
PMT	Power Measurement Toolkit
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
PPF	PolyPhase Filterbank
RDMA	Remote Direct Memory Access
RoCE v2	RDMA over Converged Ethernet version 2
TCC	Tensor-Core Correlator
TCBF	Tensor-Core Beam Former
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UBx	Université de Bordeaux
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
VIRAC	Ventspils International Radio Astronomy Centre
VLBI	Very Long Baseline Interferometry

Abstract

This deliverable describes the correlator/beam forming applications that have been (further) developed in the first two years of the RADIOBLOCKS project. These applications make use of the (GPU) “radio blocks” that have been developed as well. We first describe these radio blocks, the innovations that go with it, their performance, and their energy efficiency. Combined with the network innovations that are described in Deliverable D4.3, these applications are being prepared for the high data rates from upgraded instruments, while profiting from the high efficiency of the common radio blocks.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable describes the various correlator applications that have been (further) developed in the RADIOBLOCKS project. A unique feature of these applications is that they are organized around “radio blocks”: a collection of GPU libraries that perform the signal-processing tasks commonly found in radio-astronomical correlator and beam-forming applications. These libraries are highly optimized, and each of them introduces new techniques to achieve high performance and energy efficiency. The use of radio blocks allows the many correlator applications to profit from the improved performance, and at the same time reduces the amount of program code that needs to be developed and maintained.

Work Package 4 of the project is about two topics: data transport from the FPGA digitizers to the GPU correlators, and the GPU correlators themselves. In both areas, we explore new techniques, and implement these innovations in the various radio blocks and applications. Deliverable D4.3 reports on the progress on data transport; this Deliverable reports on the progress on the correlator applications.

For this work, we used the NVIDIA Grace Hopper [1] systems that we obtained through this project. These highly innovative systems do not only contain the fastest GPUs to date, they provide 16 times more bandwidth between the CPU and GPU than previous GPU systems. These systems provide a good balance between I/O and compute capabilities, both of which are important for correlator applications. Throughout this document, we will provide performance and energy efficiency results obtained on these systems. Unfortunately, as these systems are tremendously popular for AI training applications, they are highly expensive and difficult to obtain. Therefore, we also keep other GPU types in mind while developing the radio blocks and the correlator applications.

The work described in this deliverable has been carried out in the first two years of the RADIOBLOCKS project (i.e., between March 1st, 2023 and February 28th, 2025).

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. In Section 2, we describe the radio blocks that form the cores of these applications. Section 3 describes the applications themselves, and how they use the radio blocks. Section 4 concludes and provides a forward look. Appendix A lists the git repositories of the radio blocks and the applications.

2 Radio Blocks

The applications described in the next section make use of the “radio blocks” (GPU libraries) that have been developed. We first describe these radio blocks.

2.1 GPU filter

The GPU filter is a newly developed GPU library. Its primary task is to filter the data, but the library also performs some other signal-processing tasks, for which it is convenient to do this close to the filter. Figure 1 depicts the operations performed by the GPU filter. The combination of the FIR filters and the FFT form a PolyPhase Filter bank, where the FFT performs the filtering and the FIR filters reduce leakage into neighboring frequency channels. Basically, the FIR filters convolve the input samples with (real-valued) weights. The library can compute appropriate weights itself. Note that computing these weights is only done during initialization and not computationally expensive, but applying the weights to the streaming data is a computationally expensive task. Optionally, the filter can perform phase and amplitude corrections to the

Figure 1: Operations performed by the GPU filter library.

filtered data (fine delay compensation and bandpass correction), neither of which is a computationally expensive task, but delay compensation is an important operation to follow a source on the sky. Finally, the filter kernel transposes the output data in a format that is accepted by the Tensor-Core Correlator library (see Section 2.3), such that the radio blocks are composable.

The primary innovation in this new GPU filter is the use of a new FFT filter library, cuFFTDx [2]. Previous GPU filters relied on the well-known cuFFT library. Unlike cuFFT, cuFFTDx invokes the FFT from the GPU code instead of the CPU code, allowing the FFT to be embedded in a (large) GPU kernel that also performs other operations (FIR filtering etc.). The big advantage is that it is no longer necessary to read and write intermediate FFT input and output data through GPU device memory anymore, whereas the old cuFFT library requires input and output data to be in GPU memory. As a result, the new filter is much faster than previous implementations. The choice for cuFFTDx has a few drawbacks though: it limits the number of channels to 32,768; there are filter configurations that exceed the GPU's register file size (resulting in poor performance); and it would complicate porting the library from NVIDIA GPUs to AMD GPUs, as AMD only has an alternative to cuFFT, but not to cuFFTDx. We therefore consider implementing a fall-back solution that uses cuFFT in case cuFFTDx cannot be used. Alternatively, the first two limitations can be circumvented by cascading multiple GPU filter instances, to create increasingly finer channels.

The new filter is designed to be flexible, whereas previous implementations are typically developed for a single instrument only. However, it is quite challenging to support a wide range of parameters and to be computationally efficient at the same time. A high degree of flexibility also means that the library must support a wide range of different input formats, as basically each instrument uses a different format to store antenna data. We solved this by allowing the library user to provide an accessor function that tells the library how to access input data (somewhat similar to a lambda function in functional programming, but without the ability to capture context). The library uses runtime compilation to create efficient GPU filter code, based on the accessor function, the filter parameters, and the capabilities of the GPU at hand.

For the FIR filters, we considered using tensor cores like we did for the Tensor-Core Correlator and Tensor-Core Beam Former libraries (see below), but as this algorithm is difficult to express efficiently as matrix-matrix multiplications, we expected no performance benefits from using tensor cores. Similarly, it has been shown that FFTs can be implemented on tensor cores [3] (basically by treating the Fast Fourier Transform as a more general Direct Fourier Transform), but the increased complexity (from $O(n \log(n))$ to $O(n^2)$) nullifies any performance benefit of using tensor cores except for a very small number of channels, so we refrained from using tensor cores in this library. We also found it challenging to implement the transpose operation in a way that works efficiently on *all* the different GPU memory types (HBM, GDDR, and LPDDR): transposing data leads to unfavorable memory access patterns for all memory types, but we found the LPDDR5 memory (used in the NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin) particularly unforgiving.

The development of the GPU filter is ongoing, but a basic filter implementation works. Figure 5a compares the performance of the new filter library to an older, cuFFT-based implemen-

Figure 2: Performance of the new filter on a Grace Hopper system, compared to the previous state-of-the-art filter.

tation, that is somewhat similar to what is currently being used by the LOFAR correlator. These results are preliminary, and subject to change. The results are obtained for `complex<int8_t>` input, 16 FIR filter taps, 64 channels, and time blocks of $3,072 * 64$ samples (plus $15 * 64$ FIR filter history samples), and include bandpass correction. Thanks to the use of `cuFFTDx` instead of `cuFFT`, we would expect an approximately 3-fold performance improvement, but we see that for smaller numbers of receivers, the performance improvement is even higher than that, due to the slow ramp up of the old filter performance graph. This is caused by the old filter implementation not providing enough parallelism for the 16,896-core Hopper GPU.

Even though this filter radio block is work in progress, it is already integrated into three of our correlator applications (see Section 3). Current efforts include implementing new features (e.g., adding real-to-complex support) and extending the range of supported parameters. Although the performance is already quite good for important use cases, there may be opportunities to increase the performance further over a wider parameter range.

2.2 VLBI delay tracking

Figure 3: Delay algorithm implemented by this radio block, the individual steps are explained in the main text.

Very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) provides the highest possible angular resolution in the radio band, with terrestrial baseline lengths fundamentally only being limited by the earth's diameter. Because the antennas in a VLBI array are separated geographically, signals from astronomical objects will arrive at different times at each antenna. Furthermore, due to earth's rotation these signals are also Doppler shifted with respect to each other. Therefore before further analysis is possible all signals need to be brought to a common frame of reference, which

in VLBI is typically chosen to be the geocentric frame. Transforming the data from each antenna to the geocentric reference frame is the purpose of this radio block.

VLBI baseband data is typically real valued and quantised using two bits per sample, meaning that four samples are packed into each byte of input data. To reduce the amount of data which has to be transferred to the GPU, expanding this two bit sampled data to floating point is performed on the GPU inside this radio block.

In the following we will refer to the time difference between an astronomical signal being received at a certain antenna and that same wavefront arriving at a fictional antenna at the geocentre simply as the delay $\tau(t)$. For terrestrial antennas this delay is at most 21ms, and the maximum delay rate is $1.5\mu\text{s/s}$.

The algorithm to mitigate the delay is shown in Fig. 3. First a coarse correction is made by shifting the data stream by n_i samples, with

$$n_i(t) = \text{round}(f_s \cdot \tau(t)), \quad (1)$$

where f_s is the sample rate, and n_i was rounded to the nearest sample. This step is usually referred to as the integer delay correction.

Integer delay compensation is performed both on the CPU and the GPU. Firstly, on the host we shift the data stream by $n_i(t_0)$ samples, where t_0 is the timestamp of the first sample of the current input buffer. Subsequent changes of the integer delay are performed inside the delay correction kernel.

The residual delay after the integer delay correction has been applied is usually called the fractional delay,

$$\tau_f(t) = \tau(t) - n_i(t)/f_s. \quad (2)$$

The fractional delay is removed by segmenting the data in windows of N samples which are small enough that τ_f is approximately constant over that interval. Typically we choose N to be a power of two in the range $128 \leq N \leq 2048$, where the choice of N is mainly motivated by which number performs best on the current hardware. An FFT is then applied to each segment and the fractional delay is removed by performing a phase shift

$$\phi(\nu_i, t_{\text{mid}}) = 2\pi\nu_i\tau_f(t_{\text{mid}}), \quad 0 \leq \nu_i < B \quad (3)$$

where B is the bandwidth, $\nu_i = i \cdot B/2N$ is the baseband frequency of the i 'th spectral point, and t_{mid} is the timestamp of the middle of the segment. The FFTs are performed from within the gpu kernel using the cuFFTDx library.

Post integer- and fractional delay compensation there is still a residual phase shift $\phi_f(t)$ present in the baseband signal. This is caused by the fact that the fractional delay correction operates on baseband frequencies while the astronomical signal, however, fluctuates at the much higher sky frequency. With

$$\phi_f(t, \nu_0) = 2\pi\nu_0\tau(t), \quad (4)$$

where ν_0 is the sky frequency of the band edge. The sky frequencies are most commonly in the range 1.4-82GHz, however, the event horizon telescope can observe at frequencies as high as 345GHz. Due to the time variability of $\tau(t)$, the main effect of Eq. (4) is to induce a Doppler shift on the data.

To compensate for this residual phase ϕ_f , the data are transformed back to the time domain using the cuFFTDx library. Each sample is then multiplied with the inverse of Eq. (4). This procedure is usually referred to as fringe rotation.

Post fringe rotation the data are real-valued and in the geocentric reference frame. At this point the data can be re-analysed at an arbitrary spectral resolution, unrelated to the spectral resolution at which the delay compensation was performed.

The delay model is supplied to the kernel as a sequence of polynomials in either single- or double precision floating point. We have implemented code to parse the delay models used by the SFXC [4] VLBI correlator¹ and convert these to the format required by the GPU kernel. Users wishing to use a different delay model should find it easy to adapt this code to their use case.

(a) Visibility phase versus time on Effelsberg (DE) - Onsala (SE) baseline. The results for SFXC and the GPU are almost the same, hence the graph shows two nearly identical curves on top of each other.

(b) Phase difference between SFXC and GPU for data shown in (a)

Figure 4: Observation of bright calibrator 3C395 in the band 1626.49-1658.49 MHz.

In Fig. 4 we show a direct comparison between this radio block and SFXC. Plotting phase as a function of time on a baseline between Effelsberg (Germany) and Onsala (Sweden) observing bright calibrator 3C395. The phases from both correlators are fully consistent with each other.

2.3 Tensor-Core Correlator

A correlator's primary task is to combine the signals from multiple receivers. Depending on the data rates and the amount of antennas, the computational requirements can be high. Therefore, many instruments use GPUs to perform this task.

The Tensor-Core Correlator (TCC) [5] is the fastest GPU correlator library to date. It derives its speed and energy efficiency from the use of *tensor cores*: special-purpose matrix-matrix multiplication units that perform matrix multiplications on limited-precision input data roughly an order of magnitude faster than regular GPU cores. Tensor cores were designed as an extension to regular GPU cores, to accelerate the computations needed for training and inference in machine learning, but they can be used for other applications as well. The TCC uses these tensor cores for the correlation computations, and hides the complexity of using tensor cores from the user of the library.

¹SFXC is the current CPU-based correlator for the European VLBI Network.

Figure 5: Performance and energy efficiency of the Tensor-Core Correlator on the Grace Hopper GH200.

The TCC library already existed when the RADIOBLOCKS project started, and was, as such, the first GPU "radio block". It connects seamlessly to the aforementioned GPU filter block. As part of the project, we maintain the TCC library. For example, we added support for the Hopper GPU, improved the build environment, developed faster benchmarking software, extended the code for energy measurements, made minor improvements to the user interface, and handled support requests from the user community. Staff from the Netherlands eScience Center ported the TCC to AMD GPUs. but this does not work on all AMD GPU types yet.

Figure 5a shows the performance and energy efficiency of the TCC library, as a function of the number of antennas. These results are obtained on the Grace Hopper systems that we acquired for this project. The figure shows results for 8-bit² and for 16-bit input; 8-bit input is faster because tensor cores perform 8-bit matrix multiplications twice as fast as 16-bit multiplications. The performance is, in most cases, hundreds of tera-operations (10^{12}) per second. To illustrate the performance gains from the use of tensor cores, we compare TCC to an older GPU correlator that does not run on tensor cores, but on regular GPU cores. Unfortunately, we could not compare it to xGPU [6], which was previously known as the fastest GPU correlator, as xGPU uses a feature (textures) that is not available on Hopper GPUs anymore. Therefore, we compare it to correlator code that is similar to what is being used in the LOFAR correlator. The figure shows that TCC is roughly an order of magnitude faster.

The energy efficiency of the TCC on the Grace Hopper is shown in Figure 5b. This is the energy measured of the Hopper GPU itself, not the energy use of the whole system. The energy efficiency is about 25% lower than what was reported in [5] on a previous-generation A100 GPU. The reason for this is that the Grace Hopper's default power settings are highly aggressive: it prefers performance over energy efficiency and allows the TCC to draw over 700 Watt of power, while the A100 GPU is severely restricted by a 250 Watt power limit.

A well-known technique to increase the energy efficiency is to reduce the GPU clock speed [7]. This reduces performance, but typically reduces the energy use by a larger amount, down to a

²Wherever we refer to n -bit complex data, we mean n bits for the real part plus n bits for the imaginary part of the data.

Figure 6: The results from reducing the GPU clock frequency.

point that the maximum energy efficiency is reached. Figure 6 shows the results from reducing the GPU clock frequency of the Grace Hopper. The results are shown for 576 receivers and 8-bit input, but the method works similarly for other parameters. Figure 6a shows that the performance decreases proportionally when reducing the clock frequency in small steps. This is expected for a compute-bound operation: halving the clock speed halves the amount of operations performed. Figure 6b shows that the power use does *not* scale proportionally: at the highest frequencies, the power use decreases rapidly, but the power reduction decays at low clock speeds. Figure 6c shows the energy efficiency: the quotient of the performance and the power use. The highest energy efficiency is achieved around 1.16 GHz. At this speed, the correlator is 56% more energy efficient than at its default (1.98 GHz) speed. Clock frequency tuning thus provides the user with the opportunity to trade performance for energy efficiency.

On the Hopper GPU, the performance and energy efficiency could even be increased further if we would have used a new programming interface for tensor cores (known as *Warp Group Matrix Multiply Accumulate*), rather than the “old” interface (*Warp Matrix Multiply Accumulate*). We estimate that the performance would increase by several tens of percents, but only for larger amounts of receivers. Unfortunately, this would require a full reimplementation of all GPU code, an effort that can take easily several months, as the new API is even more complex to the old one (it is not only the tensor-core API that has changed, the new API is coupled with new asynchronous memory operations and new synchronization methods). We consider if the expected performance gains would be worth the implementation effort. A major drawback of the new API is that it only works on NVIDIA Hopper, and not on other GPU types that we also want to support (Ampere, Ada, and AMD GPUs), so we would need to maintain two implementations for the foreseeable future then.

We also consider other improvements, such as the support for single-polarized input and the option to specify subsets of the output polarizations XX,XY,YX,YY for use processing pipelines that do not always need all four output polarizations (like AARTFAAC).

2.4 Tensor-Core Beam Former

Whereas a correlator combines the signals from multiple antennas to create sky images, a beam former combines signals for time-domain observations (e.g., observing Fast Radio Bursts or pulsars). A beam former amplifies the signals from one or multiple directions, while attenuating the signals from other directions.

The *Tensor-Core Beam Former (TCBF)* is a newly developed radio block that performs the computations for beam forming on a GPU. Like the Tensor-Core Correlator, it uses the computational power from GPU tensor cores to accelerate signal processing. In general, to be able to perform computations on tensor cores, the algorithm should be expressible as matrix-matrix multiplications, and it should operate on limited-precision input (up to 16 bits). For beam forming, the latter condition is easily met, as the Analog-to-Digital converters that digitize the signals typically produce limited-precision samples. The former condition is met if a (large) number of beams is made simultaneously, and if the weights that steer the pointing directions are constant for some time. To observe a large part of the sky, many beams are made simultaneously (which makes beam forming a computationally expensive operation). And as beam forming often takes place on shorter baselines (otherwise the beams become very narrow), the (differential) beam weights do not change rapidly over time. Hence, tensor cores form a viable technology to accelerate beam forming.

The development of the TCBF was a major effort, but was done with partners from within as well as outside the RADIOBLOCKS project (the Netherlands eScience Center and the Center for Ultrasound and Brain Imaging at the Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam). Beam forming as a basic signal processing algorithm finds its use cases in several application domains. A generic, composable beam-forming library was developed. It exposes two different APIs to resolve domain-specific nomenclature confusions between, for example, the radio-astronomical and medical ultrasound applications, where the term “channel” has a different meaning in either context. The complexity of using tensor cores is hidden in the low-level library.

Figure 7: Blood flow inside a mouse brain in three orthogonal projections. Courtesy of Pieter Kruizinga.

Whereas we use beam forming to observe the sky, the medical use case is to observe the blood flow in brains, in real time (see Figure 7). A custom-made device uses ultrasound to detect the Doppler shifts caused by these blood flows. These signals are beam formed on a GPU to obtain spatial sensitivity. Due to the large data volumes and limited power budget for processing, they store and process measurements as single-bit (complex) values. We mostly focused on 16-bit beam forming, but the tensor-core methodology is rather similar (except for the complication that a signed single-bit value is stored as a 0 or 1, but represents the value -1 or 1).

Figure 8: Performance and energy efficiency of the Tensor-Core Beam Former on the Grace Hopper GH200.

Figure 8a compares the performance of the TCBF to the old LOFAR beam former, that runs on the regular GPU cores. The benchmark creates 1,024 beams (LOFAR does not create that many beams yet, but after the COBALT upgrade, we want to be able to form this many beams). For large numbers of receivers, the performance difference is over an order of magnitude, but for the typical LOFAR use case, which beam forms the 48 High-Band Antenna fields or the 24 Low-Band Antenna stations in the central core, the performance increase is a factor of 7.5 or 3.9, respectively. The increase in energy efficiency is shown in Figure 8b. Similar to what was described in the previous subsection, computational performance could be traded for energy efficiency by reducing the GPU clock frequency, but we do not repeat this exercise here. The performance for the medical use case (not shown in the figure) is even higher than that for the radio-astronomical use case: 3,700 teraops/s. This is because they operate on single-bit (complex) input data.

The TCBF has been integrated into the COBALT correlator (see Section 3.2. A paper on the TCBF has just been accepted for the 39th IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS'25) [8], one of the top-ranking conferences in High-Performance Computing. More details on the TCBF can be found in the paper.

2.5 Coherent dedispersion

We planned a GPU radio block for coherent dedispersion, but work on this has not started yet. This is planned for the third year of the project.

2.6 Data Plane Development Kit

Unlike the radio blocks above, the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) is neither a GPU library, nor a block that we developed ourselves. It is a toolkit that our correlator applications can incorporate to receive network packets from the digitizers at high speed and with low overhead. As this method is described extensively in Deliverable D4.3, we only summarize it as follows: it

is extremely fast (we demonstrated 1.2 Tb/s on the Grace Hopper), but there is a nonzero CPU overhead and GPU overhead, and it will not be easy to integrate the toolkit with existing correlator applications like COBALT and AARTFAAC. Before we continue with DPDK, we first want to study a new, alternative method (DOCA Data Path Accelerator). After that, we will decide on which high-speed data receipt technique to use in the applications.

2.7 CUDA wrappers

The CUDA wrappers are a collection of header files that simplify the use of NVIDIA libraries. Each header “wraps” a different NVIDIA library, such as the CUDA Driver API or cuFFT. They are not a true “radio block”, as they are not specific for radio astronomy, but application-domain independent. Also, unlike the other radio blocks, the wrappers are used in the CPU code that controls the GPUs, not in the GPU code itself. The wrappers have been evolving over the past decade, and have been used in many of our GPU applications, as well as the other radio blocks.

The wrappers use C++ features to provide automatic resource management (i.e., deallocating objects that are not longer used). Also, they test for errors (e.g., memory allocation failures) and throw an exception if something goes wrong, so that the user of the wrappers does not have to check for errors at all places in the code where an NVIDIA library call is invoked.

Another important feature of the CUDA Driver API wrapper is the seamless integration with runtime compilation. Basically, we compile all GPU code at runtime, i.e., when the correlator application is already started on the CPU, and is initializing everything. At that time, important parameters like the number of receivers, channels, integration time, etc. are known. By using runtime compilation, the GPU code is optimized for the given set of parameters. Another important advantage of using runtime compilation is that it allows much more readable GPU code (this is related to the use of multi-dimensional arrays, for which the dimensions need to be compile-time constants).

Within the project, we extended the wrappers with new features, such as support for the NVIDIA Management Library (NVML) library. Together with the Netherlands eScience Center, we recently added some (basic) support for AMD GPUs. This allows us to control AMD GPUs as if they were NVIDIA GPUs, which increases portability. We plan to write a short paper on the CUDA wrappers.

2.8 Power Measurement Toolkit

The *Power Measurement Toolkit (PMT)* [9] is a library that provides a generic interface to measure the power consumption of some device during a specified time interval. It hides the details of accessing the (internal) power meters of different devices: CPUs and GPUs from different manufacturers, but also external power meters like PowerSensor [10], and provides uniform interface to measure power (in Watt) and energy (in joules). We combine the values reported by PMT with the number of (useful) operations performed by a GPU kernel to establish the energy efficiency of a GPU kernel on a specific device. We use the performance and the energy efficiency as the two most important metrics for which we optimize the (GPU) program code. Like the CUDA wrappers, PMT is a generic library and not specific to radio astronomy.

Within the RADIOBLOCKS project, we maintain the PMT library. For example, we added support for Grace Hopper and AMD GPUs. PMT is mostly used by the other radio blocks, to determine the energy efficiency of the GPU kernels that we developed. The DPDK demo correlator application also uses PMT.

3 Correlator/beam former applications

In this section, we describe the correlator and beam former applications. These applications have been newly developed, or are existing applications that have been improved in the course of this project.

3.1 The AARTFAAC correlator

AARTFAAC is a transient detector that creates an all-sky image every second. It reuses the filtered signals from 576 individual LOFAR Low-Band Antennas (LBAs) in the central core, and operates almost independently of LOFAR observations.

The AARTFAAC correlator has limited functionality: it filters and correlates the LBA data in real time, but it does not even have the capability to follow sky sources, as for all-sky images, it always points at the zenith. Despite its limited functionality, parts of the code are highly complex, such as the (timestamp-based) synchronization of all CPU threads, that take care of handling network packets with input data, the orchestration of GPU tasks, and the writing of visibility output. Currently, the correlator is not in production use, pending the upgrade of the LOFAR stations.

The AARTFAAC correlator was the first application to include “radio blocks” libraries: the *GPU filter* and the *Tensor-Core Correlator*. The incorporation of these libraries removed much of the GPU kernel complexity out of the application, as this complexity is now hidden inside the respective libraries. The two libraries connect seamlessly, and ensure high performance, especially since the Tensor-Core Correlator’s performance stands out for large numbers of antennas. The only GPU code that is not in a radio block is a simple and AARTFAAC-specific transpose kernel.

Figure 9 shows an all-sky image that has been processed through the AARTFAAC correlator. The image quality cannot be compared to that of standard LOFAR images, as far fewer antennas have been used, the observation bandwidth is much lower, and the integration time is only one second instead of many hours. But its ability to observe the whole visible part of the sky is what it distinguishes from LOFAR’s capabilities.

3.2 COBALT, the LOFAR correlator/beam former

COBALT is the name of the LOFAR correlator and beam former. Currently, the LOFAR station electronics and hardware are being upgraded. Once the upgrade has completed, all Low-Band Antennas and High-Band Antennas can be used simultaneously, which was not possible before.

The COBALT hardware will also be upgraded with new, tensor-core enabled GPUs. We prepare COBALT for the higher station data rates and for the generation of 8 times more tied-array beams. For this, the Tensor-Core Beam Former was developed as a separate radio block (see Section 2.4), and this radio block has been integrated in COBALT. Other GPU kernels have been optimized, so that they run much faster on modern GPUs.

The CPU code has also been modernized. This restructuring removed outdated dependencies and simplified the code base, improving flexibility and maintainability. Obsolete libraries and programming tools like Boost multiarray were replaced by modern libraries like xtensor. The code that controls the GPUs has been improved by incorporating the CUDA wrappers radio block (see Section 2.7). The inclusion of the CUDA wrappers (see Section 2.7) further simplifies the code. The build environment has been updated, while refactoring all test cases to use Catch2 resulted in a more robust testing framework. Benchmarks were implemented to evaluate individual kernels and the entire beamforming pipeline on current hardware, complemented by

Figure 9: All-sky image, created from recorded LOFAR Transient Buffer Board data, and processed with the AARTFAAC correlator and imaging/calibration pipeline.

PMT integration for detailed energy usage analysis. New features were introduced to extend functionality, such as half-precision floating point support in the CoherentStokes kernel, optimizations for broader time integration factors, and a simpler, more robust Quantization kernel. The adoption of cuFFTDx for FFT operations within the CoherentStokesTranspose and FIR_Filter kernel reduce the amount of data movement from and to GPU memory, improving pipeline throughput. Finally, we created a new Filter kernel that consolidates these two kernels for even greater efficiency. These extensive improvements and innovations have made the coherent beam-forming pipeline significantly faster, more energy-efficient, and easier to maintain.

In the remainder of the project, we plan to include the GPU filter and Tensor-Core Correlator radio blocks (see Sections 2.1 and 2.3) in the correlator pipeline of COBALT. We also plan to incorporate DPDK (or something similar) to allow higher input data rates.

3.3 The DPDK demo correlator

The DPDK demo correlator is not a true production correlator, but a mock-up application that has been specifically developed to support research on high-speed data transport from the FPGA digitizers into a GPU correlator. The techniques that we explored to obtain high data rates, are described in Deliverable D4.3, hence we only briefly describe the application in this document.

The DPDK demo correlator uses the *Data Plane Development Kit* to receive network packets with data from the FPGA digitizers as a high data rate. It incorporates the GPU filter and Tensor-Core Correlator radio blocks, hence nearly all the GPU-specific code is included through these libraries. Normally, the GPU filter processes data with input samples that has been preloaded in GPU memory by the application, but for this application, the GPU filter takes it input directly from network packets. To avoid that the GPU filter radio block would require any knowledge of

networking, we devised an interface where the application provides the library with an accessor function that tells the library how to access data in network packets. This way, we separated the application's networking program code from the GPU library's signal-processing code, as mixing such codes would have violated any best practice or standard in software development.

Performance results from this correlator are reported in Deliverable D4.3.

3.4 Effelsberg Cryogenic Phased Array Feed

The Cryogenically Cooled Phased Array Feed (CryoPAF) Demonstrator Project (RADIOBLOCKS WP 3.1.5) includes a software correlator component, which will be implemented as part of the modular PAF processing toolkit currently under development in RADIOBLOCKS WP 5.5. Within this framework, the Tensor-Core Correlator block has been integrated into the DADAFLOW asynchronous processing framework, also developed under WP 5.5. DADAFLOW is designed for asynchronous directed acyclic graph (DAG) processing, enabling low-latency radio astronomy backends. It also provides tools for the manipulation and introspection of the multi-dimensional data types commonly used in digital interferometry.

To accommodate the high data rates from CryoPAF — exceeding 4 Tb/s — a multi-purpose backend cluster has been deployed at the Effelsberg radio telescope site. This instrument, named EDGAR, is equipped with 64 NVIDIA L40 GPUs and receives digitized, channelized inputs from CryoPAF over a dedicated 800 GbE network. Given the characteristics of the feed, only the core functionality of the correlator is required to process the 1024 frequency channels from each of the 256 PAF elements.

The CryoPAF demonstrator is not expected to be available until late 2025. However, integration of the FPGA-based channelizer systems with the EDGAR cluster will begin in the second half of this year, enabling performance testing of the correlator at scale. In the shorter term, a 7-element prototype PAF is under development at MPIfR in Bonn, utilizing the same element design as the full array. This prototype will enable on-sky testing at reduced data rates before the end of the year.

3.5 The e-Merlin correlator

The e-MERLIN interferometer is in the middle of a digital upgrade programme that is designed to make the various components of the system more modular and easily maintained in the future. Of direct relevance to the RADIOBLOCKS project are

- The replacement of the bespoke signal digitization and transport system with a digitizers that deliver VDIF formatted data over IP transport. The IP transport makes it easier to route the data, and the VDIF formatting gives better interoperability with existing software packages.
- The replacement of the specialised hardware WIDAR (Wideband Interferometric Digital ARchitecture) correlator with a software correlator. The WIDAR correlator design is around 20 years old and contains components that are now impossible to replace when they fail.

There are several challenges to operating the e-MERLIN telescope because it operates in a baseline regime (100km) where the signal fibre-transport delays are significant and diurnally variable due to thermal effects. The interferometer operates with a single central maser time standard, and so for successful coherent correlation over long time periods this variable delay must be measured and accounted for in the delay model for the software correlator in real-time. The existing software correlators have typically been designed for VLBI use where each

telescope has its own time reference where the data are recorded locally so that there is effectively no variable transport delay component. In addition, the traditional operational mode for VLBI has not been real-time correlation, although that mode is now becoming more common. One of the goals of the RADIOBLOCKS work for e-MERLIN is to adapt the delay model generation components to be able to work more flexibly in a real-time fashion that can include the variable transport delay component. This work is still in the early stages of prototyping how to deliver the transport delay measurements to the SFXC software correlator, as the transport delay measurement component of e-MERLIN itself is still in development.

Although the correlator has yet to see a first fringe with real astronomical signals, it is expected that this will be achieved in 2025, as the signal path has been proved with synthetically generated signals at the digitizers. This was made possible with the help of development at JIVE that extended the SFXC correlator to be able to process 4-bit sampled data, in addition to the 2-bit digitisation that is usual for VLBI operation.

3.6 ISBI, the VIRAC correlator

The VIRAC team using Irbene Single Baseline Interferometer (ISBI), which consists of two parabolic antennas, RT - 32 (32m diameter) and RT - 16 (16m diameter), achieved the first fringes in 2018 [11]. Since then ISBI science cases were developed. ISBI as interferometer lacks sensitivity and resolution comparing to other interferometers due to the short baseline length (approx. 800 m) and sparse UV coverage, but with high it is possible to have better sensitivity observations than a single dish with high cadence. The science cases and technological developments are described in [12], [11], and [13].

To further develop ISBI, we decided to reuse the code for the AARTFAAC correlator; it was adapted for ISBI. This module should be capable of handling ISBI data by reading both UDP sockets (for real-time observations) and VDIF files. The VDIF file reader was developed by the VIRAC team. The developed code was tested on ISBI data and a first milestone was achieved by producing a plot with autocorrelations: the bandpass (shown in Figure 10) matches with what is expected for the receivers. Next steps will be to implement support for delay compensation, and to try to detect fringes in the crosscorrelations.

3.7 The Korean VLBI correlator and High-Speed Network Based VLBI Data Stream Transfer

KASI has been developing a GPU-based correlator for KVN and EAVN correlation. The GPU-based correlator began operation in 2025 for the correlation of some observations. The GPU correlator is implemented in C++ code with CUDA. The Fourier Transform uses CUDA's cuFFT library, and the input and output of the correlation core are configured as shared memory with independent ring buffers. The input of observation data from the recorder or storage is designed based on the network and uses RoCE v2 based on RDMA. By applying RDMA, correlation processing is possible wherever the network is connected, whether inside or outside the correlation center. To provide a user-friendly interface, a Qt5-based GUI is supported (see Figure 11). In the future, research and development are planned to improve the network performance of RDMA along with the development of a correlation core using a tensor core. Along with this, it will be upgraded to support zoom band mode and pulsar mode.

KVN, consisting of four sites in Korea, completed network configuration based on the 100GbE interface in the second half of 2023. The Daejeon Correlation Center was upgraded to 400GbE to receive up to 64 Gbps of observation data streams stably from each KVN site. Like other

Figure 10: ISBI autocorrelation results obtained using the AARTFAAC correlator with the developed VDIF file reader. Red line is right polarization and green line is left polarization. Observation is done with 8 MHz bandwidth and 256 channels is used.

VLBI institutions, KVN's network backbone is physically a public network, so it is expected that it will be difficult to guarantee constant performance at all times. This means that there is a possibility that the network will become unstable in the process of transmitting data streams to the correlation center via the network. To minimize packet loss due to this, a prototype is being designed that converts UDP-based observation data output from backends such as OCTAD into TCP packets on a NVMe based large-capacity ring buffer and transmits them to the correlation center while dynamically adjusting the number of streams according to the packet loss rate. The application of the latest technologies such as GPU and DPDK for high-speed packet transmission, reception, and conversion will also be explored.

3.8 TPGS, the ALMA Total Power GPU Spectrometer

KASI and NAOJ will develop a new Total Power GPU Spectrometer (TPGS) for four ALMA telescopes, that will quadruple the bandwidth of the current spectrometer. The TPGS is used for calibration purposes. An initial design successfully passed the SubSystem Requirements Review and Conceptual Design Review.

Due to the high data rate (4 Tb/s), this is a challenge to implement. The two main challenges are the network packet receipt (for which methods like DPDK could be a solution), and the computations to filter the data, within a tight power budget. We planned to use two instances of the GPU filter library, for coarse and fine channelization, respectively. The GPU filter is designed to support the requirements of the TPGS.

Figure 11: Correlator Control GUI and Viewer for Supporting User-friendly Interface of the KVN GPU correlator

3.9 The VLBI demo correlator

Within the RADIOBLOCKS project, JIVE is developing a VLBI GPU correlator application. In its most basic form, this correlator will integrate the VLBI delay tracking radio block, the GPU filter radio block and the Tensor-Core Correlator radio block into an end-to-end correlator that can correlate a single coarse-grained frequency channel provided by the VLBI backends for an array of up to 30 VLBI radio telescopes. This correlator should be able to support the correlation parameters such as integration time and frequency resolution, required for most continuum and spectral line observations that are done with the European VLBI Network (EVN). Integration of these radio blocks is not complete yet, but it is anticipated that this will happen within the next few months. Until that integration is completed the correlator uses reference implementations for the functionality provided by the GPU filer and Tensor-Core Correlator blocks.

This basic correlator will not support more advanced observation modes such as coherent de-dispersion or Multi Phase Center correlation, but development of radio blocks that implement this functionality is planned for the second half of 2025. It will also not support complicated setups with multiple coarse-grained frequency channels or setups that combine coarse-grained frequency channels of different widths.

The goal here is not to build a production-ready correlator but to develop the bits of code that implement the most fundamental algorithms that are currently used to support the majority of science cases for the EVN on the advanced hardware architectures that are available now. This will allow us to evaluate whether these new hardware technologies bring significant benefits in cost, performance, and most importantly: power efficiency.

The GPU correlator will be largely compatible with the existing SFXC CPU correlator in its input, output, and correlation parameter specification. In particular the input format for specifying correlator delays and the output format will be identical to what the SFXC correlator uses. This will make validation of the correlator output possible and enables an apples-to-apples comparison between the two correlators for the cost, performance and power efficiency.

4 Conclusions

	GPU Filter	VLBI filter	TCC	TCBF	dedisp	DPDK	CUDA wrappers	PMT
Radio blocks	GPU filter						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	VLBI delay							
	TCC						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	TCBF						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	PMT						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Applications	AARTFAAC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Cobalt	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	DPDK demo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	EDGAR			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
	eMerlin							
	ISBI			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	KVN			<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		
	TPGS	<input type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>		
	VLBI demo		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					

Table 2: The dependencies between radio blocks, and between the correlator applications and the radio blocks. A check mark means that the application on radio block in the left column uses the radio block mentioned on the top row.

Legend: = done; = work in progress; = to be done in the remainder of the project.

The development of the radio blocks described in Section 2 and the integration into the correlator applications described in Section 3 are well underway. Table 2 shows the dependencies between the applications on the radio blocks, and the dependencies within the radio blocks themselves. The table does not show the work on the radio blocks and the applications themselves: most blocks and applications have been newly developed, or is existing software that underwent significant improvements.

In the remainder of the project, we foresee a slight change of focus from the radio blocks to the applications that use them. We do recognize the strength of the “radio blocks” approach: reuse of software, less code to maintain, high performance and energy efficiency, and a wide range of instruments that profit from the innovations that we brought in through these radio blocks.

A Repositories

name	repository	access
<i>radio blocks</i>		
GPU filter	https://git.astron.nl/RD/gpu-filter	on request
VLBI delay tracking	https://git.astron.nl/radioblocks/workpackage-4.1/sfxgpu	on request
Tensor-Core Correlator	https://git.astron.nl/RD/tensor-core-correlator	open
Tensor-Core Beam Former	https://git.astron.nl/RD/recruit/ccglib	open
	https://git.astron.nl/RD/recruit/beamformer-lofar	open
CUDA wrappers	https://github.com/nlesc-recruit/cudawrappers	open
Power Measurement Toolkit	https://git.astron.nl/RD/pmt	open
<i>correlator / beam-former applications</i>		
AARTFAAC	https://git.astron.nl/RD/AARTFAAC	open
Cobalt	https://git.astron.nl/lofar2.0/cobalt	open
DPDK demo correlator	https://gitlab.eso.org/alma/gpu-correlator/dpdk-correlator	on request
EDGAR	https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/mpifir-bdg/psrdada_cpp	open
	https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/mpifir-bdg/edd_paf	open
ISBI	https://github.com/VIRAC-SPACE/ISBI-AARTFAAC	open
VLBI demo	https://git.astron.nl/radioblocks/workpackage-4.1/sfxgpu	on request

Table 3: List of git repositories.

Table 3 lists the git repositories of the radio blocks and the correlator / beam-former applications. Most software is open access. Some newly developed software is available on request only, because the software is subject to major API changes, or does not meet certain quality standards yet. Such a repository will be opened as soon as a publication on it has been accepted.

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